

QUERCETIN MODULATES AMYLOID-BETA AGGREGATION IN ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE: A MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATION APPROACH

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Abstract

"Alzheimer's" disease is an increasingly widespread 'neurotoxic' disease. It is characterized by a breakdown in brain transmission and cognitive decline. The condition is primarily driven by the abnormal accumulation of misfolded 'amyloid beta' clusters. There are several types of amyloid beta, but the two most neurotoxic and physiologically responsive are senile plaques with isoforms 'A β 42' and 'A β 40'. Since these amyloid-beta senile plaques are crucial in the development of neurodegeneration, their inhibition is crucial for the fight against Alzheimer's disease. The neuroprotective and antioxidant properties of plant secondary metabolites, particularly flavonoids, have recently come to the forefront of scientific inquiry. Some research suggests that quercetin may inhibit the production of amyloid and effectively control oxidative stress. We used molecular dynamics simulations to learn more about the interactions between quercetin and the targeted A β 42 fibril in this study. We used the CHARMM27 force field for performing molecular dynamics simulations. Different analysis including 'Hydrogen bond analysis', 'RMSD', 'RMSF', 'SASA', and 'DSSP' were performed. Analysis of the radius of gyration shows that quercetin binding improves structural compactness and decreases conformational variations. The molecular level connection between quercetin and 'A β 42 fibrils' are explained in this paper, which also provides evidence to quercetin's therapeutic potential as a drug that can prevent A β 42 aggregation.

INTRODUCTION

There are a number of 'neurodegenerative' diseases that may lead to dementia; mostly common of these is 'Alzheimer's disease' (AD), but 'Parkinson's disease', 'Lewy body dementia', and 'Huntington's disease' all play a role (Manoharan et al., 2016). The

brain's A β 42 plaques and neurofibrillary tangled structures are mainly responsible for the ongoing neurodegeneration in AD (Pathak et al., 2022; Przedborski, 2016). This isoform accumulates more rapidly and is regarded as the most toxic version. As

a consequence of this aberrant buildup, neurofibrillary tangled structures and hazardous oligomers are created. These toxic accumulations might possibly impair neural transmission, leading to dementia, cognitive decline, and behavioural alterations (Przedborski, 2016). The WHO report indicates that around 10 million new dementia cases arise annually, with AD's accounting for 60% to 70% of these occurrences among adults (Tröster, 2008). APP proteolytic cleavage is closely related to disease development. APP is a typical transmembrane protein (Allan Butterfield, 2002; Gupta & Goyal, 2016). Evidence indicates that soluble 'amyloid beta', cleaved by 'β-secretase' through the 'non-amyloidogenic' pathway, fulfils various 'physiological roles', such as regulating 'synaptic activity', promoting neuronal growth and survival, and offering defence against 'oxidative' stress and 'neuroactive' agents (Gupta & Goyal, 2016).

When APP is hydrolysed by β-secretase via the amyloidogenic pathway, insoluble Aβ peptides are formed. Oligomers are formed when these peptides participate in self-assembly. These serve as precursors for the formation of protofibrils, which quickly aggregate into hydrophobic fibrils characterized by β-pleated sheets through the process of fibrillation (Casella et al., 2022).

Researchers have been looking at natural chemicals for years to see whether they may be safe, non-toxic substances that could be used for a long time. An important component of AD is the aggregation of amyloid-beta, hence these bioactive medicinal substances should be able to prevent this process. These substances need to have neuroprotective characteristics to mitigate the symptoms of AD or, at a minimum, to slow its progression (Li et al., 2022). Specifically, they must follow '**Lipinski's Rule of Five**' (Tahami Monfared et al., 2022), a universally recognized criterion in drug research that aids in forecasting oral bioavailability. Numerous natural compounds have therapeutic benefits. Nonetheless, the majority of plant-based compounds are unable to cross the BBB. This limits their use in the care of neurological diseases (Dar & Glazner, 2020).

Terpenoids, phenol compounds, and alkaloid are some of the secondary metabolites of plants that have been studied. It has long been known that

flavonoids, a class of phenolics, are bioactive molecules with neuroprotective qualities that are both safe and effective. Resveratrol, myricetin, EGCG, and quercetin are only a few of the phenolic substances that have shown very effective in preventing neurological diseases (Harrison et al., 2007).

Quercetin emerges as a potential neuroprotective drug. Naturally occurring flavonoid. The rationale for selecting quercetin as an amyloid-beta modulator lies in its potent capacity to destabilise the internal architecture of Aβ42, which in turn reduces the production of Aβ senile plaques (Longo & Massa, 2004). It diminishes oxidative stress, alleviates inflammation, and inhibits cognitive loss. Furthermore, it is essential for cardiovascular health (Leucuta, 2014).

One common natural compound with several uses, quercetin may one day be able to reverse the effects of 'AD' and other degenerative diseases linked to inflammatory conditions and 'oxidative' stress (Riaz et al., 2023).

Quercetin is the chemical of interest in this investigation. The subclass of flavonoids into which it falls is the flavonol subclass. With three rings denoted as A, B, and C, respectively, the system displays planar geometry and is arranged in a 'C6-C3-C6' arrangement (Fang et al., 2023). The ortho-dihydroxy groups that make up Ring B are known as a catechol ring. An neighboring 'C2=C3' double bond is resonant with the 4-oxo group contained in the heterocyclic ring C (Ugoeze & Odeku, 2025). Ring A's OH groups, Ring B's catechol groups, and Ring C's keto groups are mostly responsible for the 'antioxidant properties'. Three intramolecular bonds of hydrogen may be formed by quercetin. Two of the contacts on ring B involve molecules of carbonyl, while one involves 'hydroxyl groups'. It may be able to handle certain transition metals effectively, such as "Cu+, Mn+, and Fe+".

Quercetin has a 'molecular mass' of '302.236 g/mol' and a chemical formula of 'C15H10O7' (Salehi et al., 2020) which looks like a 'yellow crystalline powder'. This molecule is 'lipophilic' and generally insoluble in cold water. However, it shows some solubility in hot water and aquatic alkaline solutions. The flavonol quercetin is obtained from plants and is typically taken 25-50 mg daily. You may find it in the

peel of apples and red onions, two typical foods (PAUDEL, 2016). Apple peels contain '2-7 mg' of quercetin per 100 g, but red onions have 28-49 mg. Quercetin is easily available since it is found in natural sources. Because it is not very soluble in

water, its absorption through the mouth is low. Two to three hours is its half-life (Mancarz et al., 2023). Nanoparticles or liposomes are common forms of its encapsulation for use in the therapy of neurological disorders because they increase its bioavailability and distribution to the brain (Xu, 2019).

FIGURE.1. Shows the structural formula of quercetin compound

The current study uses all-atom of MD simulations to investigate the interactions between molecules between quercetin and A β 42 fibrils. Since quercetin is a natural anti-amyloidogenic and neuroprotective medicine, understanding its inhibitory mechanism was our primary goal. This technique allowed us to understand the binding mechanism of quercetin to A β -42 fibrils, destabilizing their structural integrity

potentially inhibiting aggregation. The primary objective of the research was to investigate how quercetin exerts its inhibitory effect. The structural changes caused by quercetin's binding to A β 42 fibril are discussed, in addition to the potential impacts on solvent accessibility, hydrogen bonding patterns, and surface area.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

In this review of the literature, we will look at quercetin's therapeutic potential against AD, the methods used in in 'vitro' and in 'vivo' studies, the problems with bioavailability, and the ways that new delivery technologies might improve its therapeutic effectiveness.

Recent research by Ghareeb et al. (2024) thoroughly examines the chemistry and antioxidant capabilities of 'quercetin', which safeguard the brain by mitigating 'oxidative stress' and 'inflammation', as well as its therapeutic implications in various illnesses. However, its oral bioavailability to the brain is diminished owing to inadequate water solubility. This research also proposed using nanoparticle compositions to improve distribution to the brain. 'MD simulations' conducted by Fang et al. (2023) studied how quercetin interacted with A β 42 dimers

as a function of dosage. This work included exposing A β 42 dimers to two distinct ratios of quercetin, namely 1:5 and 1:10, and simulating the interactions for a duration of 300 ns. The findings demonstrated that quercetin changed the SS of A β -42 molecules, leading to a decrease in β -sheet quantity and an increase in the formation of random coils. The effects were apparent due to the decrease in the RMSD. The '1:10' system had stronger bonds of 'hydrogen' and binding energy of around '~80 kcal/mol', indicating more stable connections. Yu et al. (2020) found that 'quercetin', at dosages ranging from '10-80 μ mol/L', may have improved neuronal survival and reduced "A β 25-35-induced cytotoxicity" in an in vitro study using a 'PC12' cell model that had been harmed by the chemical. Sabogal-Guáqueta et al. (2015) studied quercetin's effects on mice with AD's model (3 \times Tg-AD). Mice

treated with ‘25 mg/kg’ every 48 hours for three months showed considerable improvements in memory without side effects, and there was a marked reduction in ‘amyloid-beta’ accumulation and ‘tau protein tangles’.

The effects of quercetin on the cholinergic system were investigated by Liao et al. (2022). The researchers used a mix of ‘molecular docking’, ‘spectroscopic’ studies, and in vitro experiments on

Table 1. Modeling and simulation details for all-atom MD of ‘2BEG fibril’ alone and ‘2BEG fibril-Quercetin’ systems.

System	2BEG fibril alone	2BEG fibril-Quercetin
Duration of Simulation	200 ns	200 ns
Dimensions of Box	6.884 × 6.884 × 6.884 nm	6.884 × 6.884 × 6.884 nm
Molecules of Water	9943	9943
No. of ions (Na ⁺ , Cl ⁻)	29, 29	29, 29
Temperature	300 K	300 K
Pressure	1 atm	1 atm
Total atoms	1870	1902

RESULTS:

The present research shows the molecular level interaction of Quercetin with Aβ42 fibril (2BEG). The present research set out to investigate how binding quercetin affected the structural integrity and stability of Aβ42 (2BEG) fibril, an essential protein in amyloidogenic processes. AD. This work used all-atom MD simulations on two systems: one with the Aβ42 (2BEG) fibril alone and another with ‘quercetin’ along with the Aβ42 (2BEG) fibril for about 200 ns. The conformational behavior of these

PC12 cells that had been injured by Aβ25-35 to assess the adherence of quercetin to ‘acetylcholinesterase (AChE)’. According to their findings, quercetin may be found at both the catalysis and ‘peripheral active’ sites, and was stored at a rate of 200 ps. The trajectories that were collected were shown using the VMD application. As part of the GROMACS evaluation, which includes Xmgrace, they were evaluated.

systems was examined by analyzing MD trajectories using various techniques, and the findings were shown using VMD (visual molecular dynamics). Cluster Analysis, SS, Rg, RMSD, and SASA are only a few examples of such studies. Based on the findings, quercetin consistently binds to Aβ42 (2BEG) fibrils. This interaction decreases the stability of the Aβ42 (2BEG) fibrils, suggesting that quercetin may be one of the compounds responsible for this destabilization.

TRAJECTORY ANALYSIS:

FIGURE. 2.(a,b,c) Examining the 2BEG fibril's MD trajectory in water at certain time periods shows how it behaves structurally during the simulation. After equilibration, the system remained relatively unchanged at 0 ns. There were no notable changes in 2BEG's conformation at 200 ns, indicating that it was stable and unaltered. The results demonstrate that the 'charmm-27 force field' is capable of effectively retaining 'beta-sheets'.

FIGURE.3. (a,b,c) Images captured of the '2BEG-Quercetin complex' at 0, 100, and 200 ns period. There is a considerable reduction in the distance between the ligand and the critical residues 'LEU17 (23.69 Å)', 'VAL40 (33.27 Å)', and 'GLY38 (29.50 Å)' at 0 ns. The distance between the ligand and ALA40 is 9.03 Å after 100 ns. At 200 ns, the ligand got '3.94 Å' closer to 'GLY33'. This shows that the binding is strong and the structure stays stable over time.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE.4. (a,b) Images captured during a 200 ns combination of '2BEG' and 'Quercetin' show that the ligand is securely located inside the binding region of the protein.

STRUCTURE ANALYSIS

Root Mean Square Deviation:

To evaluate the long-term global (minimum energy) structural stability of a molecular system, RMSD analysis is an essential tool in MD simulation. The selected amyloid fibril, 2BEG, is an exceptionally stable pentameric structure. RMSD is greatly affected by the changes in protein's stability. In this work, the A β 42 (2BEG) fibril's behaviour is examined over time utilising RMSD analysis in two different systems: one using the protein alone and the other with quercetin.

Understanding the modifications to conformation that take place following ligand binding is crucial for therapeutic applications. We compare the 'RMSD' in both the inclusion and the absence of ligand to find the conformational stabilities. Throughout this 200 ns trajectory, we see that the RMSD of the two systems differs significantly. When quercetin is not present ('protein alone'), the 'RMSD' of individual protein molecules increases sharply during the first 20 ns peaking at around 3.5 nm. This is similar to the early phases of the simulation when the system is equilibrated and kinetic energy is redistributed among the atoms. Rather from reaching a steady state, the RMSD fluctuates continuously, peaking at a value of around 4 nm. When quercetin is not present, the A42 fibril might dynamically unfold partially inside the fibril core, as shown by these variations during the simulation time. In the

presence of quercetin, there is a modest increase in the RMSD from around 3 nm to 4 nm and 4.2 nm during the first 10 ns and from "30 ns to 65 ns", compared to when quercetin is not present. The results indicate that quercetin is trying to find a good binding spot in the A β 42 fibril core. The A β 42 (2BEG) fibril will engage in interactions such as hydrogen bonding, π - π stacking with 'aromatic residues', and 'hydrophobic' interactions when this happens.

The 'RMSD' achieves a somewhat steady plateau between '70 ns and 120 ns' after this first rise, indicating that the ligand has successfully attached to the A β 42 fibril core. 'RMSD' peaks at 4.2 nm after about 175 nanoseconds, indicating that quercetin binds to certain residues and induces temporary structural alterations. The complex RMSD starts to settle again after 180 ns, which means the system has found a new stable conformation independently. Important features of quercetin's structural accommodation inside the A β 42 fibril are divulged by this 'dynamic' structure of initial ascent, 'intermediate plateau', and final stability.

Root Mean Square Fluctuation:

The 'RMSF' tool analyzes residue-level variations and the flexibility of backbone atoms following ligand binding. This is beneficial for identifying areas that exhibit significant flexibility and may contribute to

the instability of protein structural integrity. This research examines the Aβ42 fibril's atomic structure using RMSF analysis, both with and without the 'quercetin molecule'.

According to the graph, most residues have average fluctuations of '1.5 nm to 2 nm' when the ligand is not present, but 1.5 nm to 2.5 nm when the ligand is present. The fact that this rise occurs suggests that quercetin causes changes in the structure and dynamics of Aβ42 fibril. Significance of flexibility at the 'N-terminal' of the 'Aβ42 fibril' is shown by an elevated RMSF at the beginning. Mobility is caused by disorganised terminals of the Aβ42 fibril, which are not effectively connected to quercetin. Display the same pattern from 300 to 1250 residues in the intermediate metastable state, regardless of whether quercetin is present or not. Foliar structural stability is shown by the reduced variations in the 'central hydrophobic region' (17–29). 'Phe19' and 'Phe20' are examples of residues that interact hydrophobically in this area. The 'C-terminal residues', particularly 'Ile41' and 'Ala42', are the most bendable portions of the protein. Quercetin may reduce fibril integrity by acting on C-terminal stabilising connections, according to these findings. Increased oscillations near the end point to a potential degradation of terminal stacking connections, which are essential for fibril elongation.

Hydrogen Bond Analysis:

'Hydrogen bond' analysis reveals the overall amount of hydrogen bonds established within 'quercetin' and the 'Aβ42 fibril' over the simulated period. The hydrogen bond makes the molecule very stable. The constantly changing relationship between the ligand and Aβ42 fibril is uncovered in this study via the use of 'hydrogen bond' analysis. As can be seen in the figure, the overall quantity of hydrogen bonds varies between 0 and 4 during the experiment. Transient peaks approaching four hydrogen bonds are seen in the first fifty nanoseconds, indicating that the system

is more variable than usual. This examines the conformational changes of quercetin inside the advantageous binding pocket. Hydrogen bonds attain considerable stability between 50 ns and 160 ns. Typically, just one or two hydrogen bonds remain intact. Hydrogen bonding are shown to be fragile and temporary in the illustration. In the course of the simulations, they are both formed and destroyed. According to the results of this research, they represent a gentle and flexible relationship among quercetin and the fibrils, rather than a substantial contribution to the complex's overall stability.

Radius of Gyration:

During the simulation, the 'radius of gyration' shows how compact the protein fibril is overall. Aβ42 fibril structural organisation was evaluated by this study by using the Rg value to determine the effect of quercetin binding.

Whether quercetin is present or not, the typical values of Rg fall anywhere between 1.5 nm and 5.0 nm. Aβ42 fibrils show more changes in Rg, reaching 4.8 nm, when quercetin is not present. Structured flexibility and unfolding are shown by this. The presence of quercetin is associated with somewhat diminished spikes. Based on the findings, it is evident that the 'protein-ligand complex' has a more stable and constant 'Rg profile'. This might mean that the ligand makes the protein more structurally compact and reduces conformational variations.

Solvent Accessible Surface Area:

One way to measure a protein's solvent exposure is via the SASA analysis. Throughout the simulation, the only protein in this research continuously displays increased SASA values of approximately 75-85 nm². Reduced SASA values, between "70 and 80 nm²", are seen in the protein-ligand arrangement. That the 'protein-ligand' interaction allows for a more compact and folded form of the protein is shown by this decrease.

Table 2. Structural Properties on Average Over Time in a Simulation..

Parameters	Fibril (2BEG) only	2BEG fibril-Quercetin
Root Mean Square Deviation (nm)	1.3 ± 0.95	1.5 ± 0.8
Root Mean Square Fluctuatio (nm)	1.4 ± 0.2	1.5 ± 0.3
Radius of Gyration (nm)	1.9 ± 0.8	1.96 ± 0.8

Solvent Accessible Surface (nm ²)	77.5 ± 2.6	75.4 ± 3.3
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The mean ± SD is calculated based on the last 200 ns frame.

Secondary structure:

The stability of beta sheets and alpha helices over time is evaluated using the DSSP analysis. There are ‘alpha helices’, ‘beta sheets’, ‘twists’, ‘coils’, and ‘3–10 helices’ shown in this interpretation. With a reduction to less than 60 residues, the sole protein shows increased variety. Destabilisation of secondary structures is indicated by this. Throughout the simulation, the “quercetin-Aβ42(2BEG) fibril complex” maintained a larger number of repetitions in secondary structures, which is indicative of the ligand’s role in maintaining the protein’s ‘secondary structures’ and, by extension, improving overall structural stability, which ranges from 60 to 75 residues.

Table 3. The percentage composition of the secondary structure throughout the simulation

Secondary Structure(SS)	α-helix (% ± SD)	β-sheet (% ± SD)	Turns (% ± SD)	Bends (% ± SD)	Coils (% ± SD)	3-10 helix (% ± SD)	Bridge (% ± SD)
2BEG Fibril only	31.5 ± 2.1	26.5 ± 1.8	8.3 ± 0.5	7.3 ± 0.4	17.1 ± 1.04	1.7 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.1
2BEG fibril + Quercetin	36.1 ± 2.0	13.6 ± 1.3	10.4 ± 0.4	8.7 ± 0.6	20.3 ± 1.4	1.9 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.1

Cluster Analysis:

Cluster analysis sorts protein-ligand complexes with comparable conformations into groups defined by their RMSD values. Finding the most common and reliable confirmations is made easier using this method. There is stability when the number of clusters is low. Within the first 0–40 ns window, the 2BEG and quercetin compound exhibits a fluctuation of 1–2 clusters. This diversity demonstrates that the system is inherently unstable and subject to ‘dynamic structural’ alterations since there are several possible structural conformations. The system stabilises and acquires an even structure

when the complex converges into a single dominating cluster after 40 ns, thanks to the persistent connections between 2BEG and quercetin. As the first simulation runs, the average cluster size fluctuates between a thousand and nine hundred and fifty molecules. As the ‘protein-ligand complex’ strives towards a low-energy state, these alterations point to a dynamic structural change. Stability is maintained for over 40 ns after the cluster size reaches around 1900 molecules. The complicated system has achieved structural stability, as this peak suggests.

FIGURE.5. (a) Following changes in response to quercetin binding events, the 2BEG-quercetin complex's RMSD profile stabilises after 180 ns, indicating that quercetin is conformationally stable.(b) The RMSF graphic shows that the 2BEG regions become more flexible as quercetin is bound. The centre core remains stable, preserving the fibril structure, but the terminal portions show more variations, indicating that quercetin affects terminal stacking. (c) The hydrogen bonding graph of quercetin with '2BEG' indicates that the number of bonds fluctuates between zero and four throughout the simulation process. The significant binding stability is shown by quercetin forming '1-2 hydrogen bonds' with the protein's structure in a typical simulation. (d) The Rg figure shows that the 2BEG-quercetin combination is more compact when there are modest variations. The 2BEG fibril is unique in that it shows signs of unfolding and enhanced flexibility via its higher spikes.

FIGURE.6. (a) The quercetin-2BEG has a more compact and folded shape, as seen by the reduced SASA values, which indicate less solvent exposure. (b) As time passes, the secondary structures of the ‘Quercetin-2BEG’ complex become more stable. (c) Over the course of a 200 ns test, the cluster graph counts the number of clusters. Once the 2BEG-quercetin complex has been stably established, the cluster number drops to 1 after 40 ns. (d) The size of the cluster becomes steady at 40 ns, suggesting that the conformation is stable.

FIGURE.7. (a) This graph only illustrates protein. Analysis of secondary structure is conducted via DSSP. Consistent beta sheets and alpha helices are seen in this graphical timeline throughout the 200 ns simulation, which indicates strong 'structural integrity'. (2BEG-quercetin) is shown in this figure (b). A partial unfolding of the protein may be occurring in certain regions, as shown by the larger white patches in the complex, which is caused by ligand binding. Here we have a look at how quercetin works mechanically; it keeps the core stable while destroying key areas that are needed for fibril elongation.

DISCUSSION:

This research delves into how a quercetin molecule interacts with Aβ42 fibril. This study shows how the stability of the structure of the Aβ42 fibril is impacted by ligand binding. According to the RMSD research, quercetin helps keep fibrils from unravelling. During the 200 ns simulation, Aβ42 fibrils show variations of around 4.0 nm when quercetin is not present. The present research shows that the fibril's structural flexibility is more than previously thought. Quercetin may prevent fibrils from aggregating into dangerous oligomers by stabilising them, which is caused by conformational changes. Quercetin enhances the compactness of the fibril's core while increasing the flexibility of its ends. The ends are crucial for fibril elongation. The stability of the core structure might be preserved while harmful aggregation is reduced, according to

this. In addition, when ligands connect to the Aβ42 fibril's core, the results from the RMSF show that its C-terminal becomes more flexible, while the rest of the fibril gets more stabilised. Fibril elongation relies on terminal π-π stacking connections, which quercetin seems to reduce. Inhibitors that can halt the formation of fibrils without destroying the protein backbone must undergo these structural changes. Also, the stable radius of gyration and lower SASA in quercetin-treated samples demonstrate that the hydrophobic residues contributing to pathogenic accumulation are more compact and are not exposed to as much light. The capacity to maintain structural conformation by preserving β-sheet content is examined in quercetin's role, as shown by the secondary structure study. These characteristics illustrate quercetin's molecular behaviour, which

stabilises the fibril in a less toxic and more compact form rather than completely degrading it. This stabilisation may reduce the fibril's ability to produce cellular toxicity. Hydrogen bond analysis investigates the interactions between quercetin and A β 42 in deeper detail. The amount of hydrogen bonds between quercetin and A β 42 may range from zero to four. These fleeting interactions show that hydrogen bonding helps find the binding site initially but doesn't help keep the quercetin-fibril complex stable. Quercetin shows promise as a treatment for AD, according to this research, which provides molecular-level data.

CONCLUSION:

This study uses all-atom MD simulations to thoroughly examine the molecular level relationship between A β 42 fibrils and small natural substances such as quercetin. We find that quercetin considerably affects the structural and conformational stabilities and uniformity of the A β 42 fibril by comparing its behaviour in 200 ns simulations when used alone and in combination with quercetin. Secondary structure, root mean square deviation, and 'radius of gyration' evaluations show that quercetin first induces oscillations, followed by a transition to a more stable structural state. Finding novel therapeutic targets to inhibit amyloid beta might be aided by our findings.

IMPLICATIONS:

This research sheds light on the chemical process that explains quercetin's interaction with 'A β 42 fibrils' in a substantial way. It strengthens the fibril's centre while weakening its ends. Quercetin may therefore be able to prevent the buildup of harmful aggregates. The efficacy of quercetin as a regulator of amyloid beta fibrillogenesis is investigated using this simulation-based approach. To enhance bioavailability, BBB permeability, and toxicity reduction, it is necessary to identify certain regions and interactions. This allows for the creation of smaller molecules that are more potent and effective. An algorithm for computerised screening of natural chemicals with the potential to target amyloid beta pathogenic fibrils is presented in this work. This study's findings suggest quercetin and its derivatives

might be a promising pharmacological option for developing amyloid beta inhibitors.

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